

Studies on the Slow Coagulation of Lyophobic Colloids : The relationship between time of Coagulation and Electrolyte Concentration

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The modified empirical relationship between time of coagulation and electrolyte concentration as given by Srivastava and Abrol has been tested in the light of experimental data on the slow coagulation of manganese ferrocyanide and antimony trisulphide sols.

Bhattacharya and co-workers¹⁻⁵ studied the variation of time of coagulation with electrolyte concentration for a number of sols and suggested the following relationship

$$c = a + \frac{m \cdot \frac{1}{t}}{n + \frac{1}{t}} \quad (1)$$

where c stands for the electrolyte concentration, t stands for the time of coagulation and 'a', m and n are constants. From equation (1) it follows that when $1/t$ approaches zero,

FIG.1 EVALUATION OF CRITICAL STABILITY CONCENTRATION

Fig. 1

FIG.2 SLOW COAGULATION OF MANGANESE FERROCYANIDE SOL WITH KCl

Fig. 2

c approaches 'a'. This means that for coagulating a sol the concentration of the added electrolyte should be greater than a , which has been called⁶ as critical stability concentration.

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Recently Srivastava and Abrol⁷ have drawn attention towards an obvious drawback in equation (1). If we substitute zero for c in equation (1), the time of coagulation t works out to be $-\frac{m+a}{a.n}$ which is absurd. This is because in the case of a stable sol no coagulation should take place in the absence of a coagulating agency and t should tend to infinity. In view of this Srivastava and Abrol suggested⁷ the following modified relationship between time of coagulation t and the electrolyte concentration c .

$$t = \frac{k}{c(c-a)} \quad (2)$$

where k is a constant. Srivastava and Abrol have also shown⁸ that equation (2) can be derived theoretically by making use of the theory of Verway and Overbeek⁹. The purpose of this communication is to report investigations on the slow coagulation of manganese ferrocyanide and antimony trisulphide sols with a view to testing the validity of equation (2) from the experimental data thus obtained.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

The coagulation studies were conducted on manganese ferrocyanide and antimony trisulphide sols. A 0.5 per cent solution of tartar emetic was added drop by drop to the water saturated with hydrogen sulphide and through which hydrogen sulphide was passed. This resulted into an orange coloured sol of antimony trisulphide.

FIG. 3 SLOW COAGULATION OF ANTIMONY TRISULPHIDE SOL WITH BaCl_2

Fig. 3

Manganese ferrocyanide sol was prepared by the method of double decomposition as described by Khan and Malik¹⁰. Potassium ferrocynide (BDH) and Manganous sulphate (S. Merck) were used for this purpose.

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Time of Coagulation. Five ml of each sol and varying amounts of solutions of Potassium chloride (A.R.) and Barium chloride (A.R.) were taken in steam dried pyrex test tube and the total volume was made up to 10 ml by adding double distilled water. The time at which the sol particles left the surface of the sol was taken to be the time of coagulation. The concentration of various electrolytes in the sol was so adjusted that the time of coagulation was near about thirty minutes, or more.

FIG.4 SLOW COAGULATION OF ANTIMONY TRISULPHIDE SOL. WITH KCl

Fig. 4

RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

The observations are recorded in Table I and II.

TABLE I

Slow coagulation of Manganese ferrocynaide sol with KCl.

Sr. No.	C mM/Litre	Time t in minutes	$\frac{1}{t} \times 10^3$	a mM/Litre	$C-a$	$C(c-a)$
1.	35	58	17.2	25	10	350
2.	37.5	53'-30"	18.7	25	12.5	468.75
3.	40	41	24.4	25	15	600
4.	42.5	33	30.3	25	17.5	743.75
5.	45	26	38.4	25	20	900

TABLE II

Slow Coagulation of Antimony trisulphide sol with BaCl₂.

Sr. No.	C mM/Litre	Time t in minutes	$\frac{1}{t} \times 10^3$	a mM/Litre	$c-a$	$c(c-a)$
1.	3.0	96'-30"	10.36	1.3	1.7	5.10
2.	3.5	75'-40"	13.2	1.3	2.2	7.70
3.	4.0	61'-45"	15.6	1.3	2.7	10.80
4.	4.5	51'-50"	19.6	1.3	3.2	14.40

The values of the critical stability concentration ' a ' were determined in each case by extrapolating the graph, obtained by plotting C against $1/t$, to $1/t = 0$. This has been demonstrated in figure 1 in the particular case of Manganese ferrocyanide sol.

It follows from equation (2) that the plot, of $C(c-a)$ against $1/t$ should be a straight line passing through the origin. In figures 2 and 3 $C(c-a)$ has been plotted against $1/t$ for the case of manganese ferrocyanide sol with Potassium chloride as coagulating agent and for the case of antimony trisulphide sol with Barium chloride as coagulating electrolytes respectively. Since the plots are straight lines passing through the origin it is concluded that equation (2) is obeyed by the coagulation data.

The data of Kumar and Bhattacharya and Bhattacharya¹ in the case of Antimony trisulphide sol with Potassium chloride as coagulating electrolyte have also been examined and plotted in figure 4. It is interesting to note that their data also obeys equation (2).

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